

Research Article

Design and *In Vitro* Biological Evaluation of a Novel Organotin(IV) Complex with 1-(4-Carboxyphenyl)-3-ethyl-3-methylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione

Nebojša Đ. Pantelić ¹

¹Department of Engineering and Natural Sciences, University of Applied Sciences Merseburg, Eberhard-Leibnitz-Strasse 2, 06217 Merseburg, Germany

²Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Nemanjina 6, 11000 Belgrade-Zemun, Serbia

³Department of Chemistry, Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade, Studentski Trg 14, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

⁴Institute of Oncology and Radiology, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

⁵Institute of Physiology and Biochemistry, Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade, Studentski Trg 16, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

Correspondence should be addressed to Nebojša Đ. Pantelić; pantelic@agrif.bg.ac.rs and Goran N. Kaluđerović; goran.kaluderovic@hs-merseburg.de

Received 24 September 2018; Accepted 3 December 2018; Published 17 January 2019

Academic Editor: Maolin Guo

Copyright © 2019 Nebojša Đ. Pantelić et al. This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

A novel triphenyltin(IV) compound with 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3-ethyl-3-methylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione was synthesized and characterized by IR, NMR spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, and elemental analysis. *In vitro* anticancer activity of ligand precursor and synthesized organotin(IV) compound was determined against tumor cell lines: human adenocarcinoma (HeLa), human myelogenous leukemia (K562), and human breast cancer (MDA-MB-453), using microculture tetrazolium test (MTT) assay. The results indicate that complex exhibited very high antiproliferative activity against all tested cell lines with IC_{50} values in the range of 0.22 to 0.53 μ M. The highest activity organotin(IV) compound expressed against the HeLa cells ($IC_{50} = 0.22 \pm 0.04 \mu$ M). The ligand precursor did not show anticancer activity ($IC_{50} > 200 \mu$ M). Furthermore, fluorescence microscopy analysis of HeLa cells reveal that organotin(IV) complex induced apoptosis as a mode of cell death, which is consistent with the increase of cells in the sub-G1 phase.

1. Introduction

Metal complexes have been successfully applied in medicine for the treatment of human diseases such as cancer, rheumatoid arthritis, and gastric and duodenal ulcers and also are in widespread use as imaging agents as diagnostics tools [1]. One of the most expanding areas in medicinal bioinorganic chemistry is research on the synthesis of new metal-based compounds and their applications in medicine as drugs [2–4]. Nowadays, cancer is one of the most threatening mankind diseases. During last five decades, over 500,000 synthetic chemical compounds have been tested for their antitumor

activity, but only about 25 of these are in worldwide use today [5]. The application of the first and most worldwide used metal-based anticancer drug, cisplatin, discovered by Rosenberg, is limited by severe side effects such as neuro-, nephro-, and ototoxicity [6–11], and therefore, the research of novel metal-based complexes with reduced toxicity and improved clinical efficacy is the subject of intensive studies into anticancer drug investigations [12–16].

Recent studies have shown very promising *in vitro* antitumor properties of organotin(IV) compounds, against a wide panel of tumor cell lines of human origin [17–21]. The organotin(IV) complexes with carboxylate [22–29], thiolato

[30–36], and dithiocarbamate [37] ligands have been extensively studied, and it was found that (carboxylato)triphenyltin(IV) and tetraorganotin(IV) compounds show the highest cytotoxic activity [22, 38]. However, the possible application of the synthesized organotin(IV) derivatives was very limited due to their poor water solubility [39]. Also, significant biological studies of organotin(IV) derivatives with benzoic acids have been reported [40–46].

Many studies demonstrated that cyclic imides such as succinimides (pyrrolidine-2,5-diones) have promising biological properties such as nephrotoxic [47], anticonvulsant [48], antimutagenic [49], and analgesic [50] activities. Additionally, it was found that they inhibit a selective monoglyceride lipase and psychiatric disorders such as anxiety and depression [51]. Therefore, attention herein was drawn to aryl-*N*-succinimide with a carboxylate substituent as ligand compound. There are numerous reports showing that there is no single or well-defined number of ways in which organotin(IV) compounds interact with the cell membrane or constituents within the cell [52–55]. Thus, the mechanism of action of organotin(IV) compounds in effecting cell death remains unclear, and further work is necessary to identify the real apoptotic or necrotic pathways that cells treated with these compounds follow to their death.

In this study, the synthesis and characterization of a triphenyltin(IV) compound containing 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3-ethyl-3-methylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione anion (CEMPD⁻) is reported. The evaluation of cytotoxic activity against tumor cell lines human cervix adenocarcinoma (HeLa), human myelogenous leukemia (K562), and human breast cancer (MDA-MB-453) has been performed. Additionally, the mode of cell death and cell cycle distribution of HeLa cells induced by synthesized complex were studied.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemicals and Methods. The ligand 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3-ethyl-3-methylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione, a racemate, was synthesized as described previously [56]. Elemental analyses were performed on an elemental vario EL III microanalyzer. A Nicolet 6700 FT-IR spectrometer and ATR technique were used for recording midinfrared spectra (4000–400 cm⁻¹) for complex. NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Avance III 500 spectrometer. Chemical shifts for ¹H, ¹³C, and spectra were referenced to internal standard TMS. Mass spectra of the compound were recorded with an Orbitrap LTQ XL instrument (Thermo Scientific, Bremen, Germany) in CH₃CN [57]. Reagents and solvents were of commercial reagent grade quality and used without further purification.

2.2. Synthesis of Complex. A suspension of the 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3-ethyl-3-methylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione (50 mg; 0.191 mmol) in distilled water (10 mL) was treated with LiOH·H₂O (8.1 mg; 0.191 mmol), the mixture was stirred for 3 h at 40°C, and a clear solution was formed. Then, 5 mL of Ph₃SnCl (73.8 mg; 0.191 mmol) methanolic solution was added dropwise into the reaction mixture. Afterwards, the solution was stirred for 3 h and white precipitate was

formed. The precipitate was filtered off, washed with 5 mL of distilled water, and then dried *in vacuo* over silica gel.

[Ph₃Sn(CEMPD)] yield: 75 mg (62%), white solid. Anal. calcd. for SnC₃₂H₂₉NO₄ × 2H₂O: C, 59.47; H, 5.15; N, 2.17. Found: C, 59.60; H, 5.19; N, 2.13. IR (ATR, cm⁻¹): 1716 (s) (ν C=O), 1642 (s) (ν_a COO⁻), 1390 (s) (ν_s COO⁻), 449 (s) (ν Sn–O). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO): |δ| ppm = 7.90 (d, 2H, –C₆H₄), 7.86 (m, 6H, *o*-H in SnPh₃, ³J(¹H–Sn) = 34 Hz), 7.39 (m, 9H, *m*- and *p*-H in SnPh₃, ⁵J(¹H–Sn) = 77 Hz), 7.26 (d, 2H, –C₆H₄), 2.78–2.62 (AB q, 2H, –C⁵H₂–), 1.70–1.58 (m, 2H, –C²H₂CH₃), 1.27 (s, 3H, –C³H₃), 0.85 (t, 3H, –CH₂C¹H₃); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO): |δ| ppm = 181.92 (C6), 175.32 (C7), 169.35 (C12), 143.46 (C8), 137.58 (C2' and C6' in SnPh₃, ²J(¹³C–Sn) = 45 Hz), 130.13 (C11), 129.26 (C10), 128.69 (C1' in SnPh₃, ¹J(¹³C–Sn) = 67 Hz), 127.01 (C3' and C5' in SnPh₃), 44.12 (C4), 127.01 (C9), 40.39 (C5), 31.27 (C2), 23.32 (C3), 8.85 (C1). HR ESI–MS (CH₃CN), *m/z*: 634.10257 [M + Na]⁺; 650.07690 [M + K]⁺.

2.3. Preparation of Drug Solutions. DMSO (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) was used for preparation of stock solutions for investigated compounds at the concentration of 10 mM. Afterwards, various working concentrations were prepared from the stock solutions diluting with the nutrient medium. The nutrient medium was RPMI-1640 (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) supplemented with 2 mM L glutamine, 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS; Biochrom AG, Berlin, Germany), and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) [57].

2.4. Cell Lines. Human cervix adenocarcinoma cell line (HeLa), human chronic myelogenous leukemia cells (K562), and human breast cancer cell line (MDA-MB-453) were grown in complete RPMI-1640 medium (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) as indicated in [57].

2.5. Determination of Cell Survival. Similarly to methods described in [57], HeLa (2500 cells/well) and MDA-MB-453 cells (3000 cells/well) were seeded into the wells of a 96-well flat-bottomed microtiter plate. Twenty-four hours later, after the cell adherence, different concentrations of investigated compounds were added to the wells, except for the controls, where only the complete medium was added. The final complex concentration range used in the experiments was 0.0625–1 μM (0.0625, 0.125, 0.25, 0.5, and 1 μM). The ligand concentration range used was 12.5–200 μM. The final concentration of DMSO was negligible for complex and never exceeded 1% for ligand, which is a nontoxic concentration for the cells [57]. For nonadherent K562 cells (5000 cells/well), the compounds were applied 2 h after cell seeding. The culture medium with corresponding concentrations of investigated compounds, but without cells, was used as blank. The cultures were incubated for 72 h, and the effects of the investigated compounds on cancer cell survival were determined using the microculture tetrazolium test (MTT), according to Mosmann [58] with modification by Ohno and Abe [59], 72 h after the addition of the

investigated compounds. Briefly, 20 μL of MTT solution (5 mg/mL of phosphate-buffered saline, PBS) was added to each well. Samples were incubated for additional 4 h at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO_2 (v/v). Afterward, 100 mL of 10 sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) was added in order to extract the insoluble formazan, which represents the product of the conversion of the MTT dye by viable cells. The number of viable cells in each well is proportional to the intensity of the absorbance (A) of light, which was measured in a microtiter plate reader at 570 nm, 24 h later [57]. To determine cell survival (%), the A of a sample with cells grown in the presence of various concentrations of the investigated compounds was divided by the control optical density (the A of control cells grown only in the nutrient medium) and multiplied by 100. The A of the blank was always subtracted from the A of the corresponding sample incubated with the target cells. IC_{50} is defined as the concentration of an agent inhibiting cell survival by 50% compared with the vehicle-treated control [57]. All experiments were performed in technical and biological triplicates.

2.6. Morphological Analysis (AO/EB Double Staining).

The mode of cell death induced by investigating compound was assessed with acridine orange (AO) and ethidium bromide (EB) double staining assay, according to the standard procedures and examined under a fluorescence microscope [60]. HeLa cells were seeded overnight on coverslips (100,000 cells/coverslip) in 2 mL of complete medium. The following day, cells were treated with complex in concentrations corresponding to $2 \times \text{IC}_{50}$ and $4 \times \text{IC}_{50}$ for the 72 h treatment. After 24 h, coverslips with target cells were stained with the acridine orange/ethidium bromide mixture (3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ AO and 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ EB in PBS) and visualized and photographed under a fluorescence microscope (fluorescence microscope-PALM MicroBeam systems, Carl Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) [57].

2.7. Cell Cycle Analysis.

HeLa cells were seeded in six-well plates (3×10^5 cells/well) and after 24 h of incubation treated with $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ ($2 \times \text{IC}_{50}$ concentration) at 37°C for the additional 24 or 48 h. The assay was performed as described in [57]. In short, after the incubation period, the cells were collected by trypsinization, fixed in ice-cold 70% ethanol for 1 h on ice, and incubated at -20°C for one week. Then, the cells were washed in PBS, and pellets obtained by centrifugation were treated with RNase (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) at 37°C for 30 min and incubated with propidium iodide (PI) (40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for at least 30 min [57]. DNA content and cell-cycle distribution were analyzed using Becton Dickinson FACSCalibur flow cytometer. Flow cytometry analysis was performed using CellQuest (Becton Dickinson, San Jose, CA, USA) software with a minimum of 20,000 cells per sample [61].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Synthesis and Characterization.

In the reaction of Ph_3SnCl and equimolar amount of 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3-

ethyl-3-methylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione, previously deprotonated with LiOH, the desired compound $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ was obtained as white product in moderate yield. The prepared compound was soluble in dichloromethane, chloroform, dimethyl sulfoxide, and acetonitrile. The synthesized compound was characterized by elemental analysis, IR, NMR spectroscopy, and mass spectrometry.

IR spectra of the synthesized compound showed strong $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching band at 1716 cm^{-1} which was similar to the ligand precursor [56], indicating that coordination of carbonyl oxygen atoms to the tin(IV) center did not occur. Additionally, strong bands were found at 1642 and 1390 cm^{-1} which correspond to the asymmetric and symmetric vibrations, respectively, of the COO moiety (ligand precursor: 1682 and 1390 cm^{-1}). Moreover, the difference between the asymmetric and symmetric vibrations of more than 200 cm^{-1} indicates monodentate coordination of the carboxylate ligand to tin(IV) center [62]. The medium absorptions corresponding to the Sn–O stretching mode of vibration appear at 449 cm^{-1} .

In the ^1H NMR spectra, a set of two signals arising from the *o*-H and *m*/*p*-H atoms of SnPh_3 moiety, at ca. 7.86 and 7.39 ppm, respectively, were observed. Furthermore, aliphatic protons of methyl and ethyl groups from the succinimide ring are on their anticipated positions [56]. Expectedly, methyl protons resonated as one strong singlet at 1.27 ppm, while those from the ethyl group were observed as multiplet (1.70–1.58 ppm) and triplet (0.88 ppm). Additionally, methylene protons in the succinimide ring ($-\text{CH}_2-$) were found as characteristic AB quartet in the range 2.78–2.62 ppm. Coupling with tin nucleus can be observed as satellites nearby resonances of *o*-H atoms from the Ph_3Sn moiety. ^{13}C NMR spectra of the synthesized compound showed expected signals at the appropriate positions. Numeration of carbon atoms is shown in Scheme 1. All carbonyl carbons are resonating at values higher than 160 ppm. Aromatic carbon atoms can easily be assigned due to visible coupling with tin through one (*ipso*-C) and two (*o*-C) bonds. Furthermore, HR ESI-MS was recorded in positive ion mode, and the $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ and $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ mass peak were detectable. Complete characterization of the synthesized compound can be seen in supplementary section (Figures S1–S7).

3.2. In Vitro Cytotoxicity.

The cytotoxic potential of ligand precursor 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3-ethyl-3-methylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione (CEMPDH) and its new synthesized organotin(IV) compound, $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$, was studied in a panel of malignant cell lines. In Figure 1 the survival of HeLa, K562, and MDA-MB-453 in the presence of different concentrations of complex are presented. The IC_{50} values for CEMPDH, $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ and cisplatin, for comparison, against investigated cell lines are summarized in Table 1 (MTT test, 72 h incubation). Cisplatin was used as a positive control. The results indicate that the ligand precursor CEMPDH did not show cytotoxic activity against all tested cell lines ($\text{IC}_{50} > 200 \mu\text{M}$). On the other hand, $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ exhibits high activity against all three malignant cell lines, the

FIGURE 1: Survival of tumor cells as a function of different concentrations of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ determined by MTT test, after 72 h incubation.TABLE 1: IC_{50} (μM) (mean \pm SD) of CEMPDH, $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$, and cisplatin (72 h of action).

Compounds	IC_{50} (μM)		
	HeLa	K562	MDA-MB-453
CEMPDH	>200	>200	>200
$[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$	0.22 ± 0.04	0.53 ± 0.01	0.28 ± 0.03
Cisplatin	6.90 ± 1.71	5.82 ± 0.17	6.73 ± 0.48

highest against HeLa cells and the lowest IC_{50} value observed against K562 cells. In comparison with cisplatin (Table 1), the IC_{50} value of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ ranges from 0.22 to 0.53 μM and novel organotin(IV) compound is 11 up to 31 times more active. Furthermore, the activity of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ is in expected range for (carboxylato)triphenyltin(IV) compounds [28, 63]. It is well known that some analogue $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{RCOO})]$ compounds (e.g., $\text{RCOO} = 4$ -methoxyphenylacetato, 2,5-dimethyl-3-furoato, or 1,4-benzodioxane-6-carboxylato) may possess relatively high selectivity towards K562 tumor cells

[28]. Namely, they can be up to four times more active against the K562 tumor cell line than that on normal rested or stimulated peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs). Thus, further studies should concern the activity of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ against normal cells.

3.3. Morphological Analysis of HeLa Cell Death. To determine the mode of cell death induced by $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ in HeLa cell line, AO/EB double staining assay was performed. Selected cell line was treated for 24 h with the concentrations of the investigated compound corresponding to $2 \times \text{IC}_{50}$ and $4 \times \text{IC}_{50}$ values obtained in MTT assay. The results from fluorescence microscopy of treated HeLa cells are showed in Figure 2.

Treatment of HeLa cells for 24 h with $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ ($2 \times \text{IC}_{50}$) induced nuclear condensation detected by freely permeable dye AO, which is a typical morphological feature of apoptosis. Higher concentration of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ ($4 \times \text{IC}_{50}$) induced a significantly higher level of apoptosis, primarily nuclear fragmentation. Furthermore, a typical feature correlated to late apoptosis, damage of the plasma membrane, could be detected by the entry of the EB into the cell and binding to the DNA (red fluorescence).

3.4. Cell Cycle Analysis. Based on the results described above, to further examine the mechanisms of action of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ in HeLa cells, determination of cell cycle distribution was performed on the basis of DNA content in HeLa cell line, after exposure for 24 and 48 h by flow cytometry analysis (PI staining). As shown in Figure 3, after exposure of HeLa cells to $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ in concentration corresponding to $2 \times \text{IC}_{50}$, number of cells in sub-G1 increases significantly in comparison with control cells (24/48 h: 1.62/3.68%, control; 9.0/10.11%, $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$). After 48 h of incubation, there is a small increase in the number of cells in the sub-G1 phase (relative to 24 h), but also a decrease in the number of cells in the S and G2/M stages relative to the control cells. It could be that cells in the S and G2/M phase are more susceptible to apoptotic stimuli than those in the G1 phase.

FIGURE 2: Fluorescent micrographs of acridine orange and ethidium bromide stained HeLa cells, untreated (a) or treated with $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ for 24 h (b) $2 \times \text{IC}_{50}$ and (c) $4 \times \text{IC}_{50}$. Arrows indicate apoptotic cells with condensed chromatin and/or fragmented nuclei while arrowheads mark necrotic cells.

FIGURE 3: Effect of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ on cell cycle phase distribution: HeLa cell lines were exposed to IC_{50} doses of organotin(IV) compound.

4. Conclusion

The synthesis of a new triphenyltin(IV) complex with 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3-ethyl-3-methylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione, $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ is described. The compound was characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ^1H , ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy, and mass spectrometry. $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ along with appropriate acid CEMPDH was tested against human adenocarcinoma (HeLa), human myelogenous leukemia (K562), and human breast cancer (MDA-MB-453), by MTT assay. The results have shown that $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ expressed excellent cytotoxicity against all mentioned cancer cell lines with the IC_{50} range from 0.22 to $0.53 \mu\text{M}$ which is 11 to 31 times higher in comparison with clinically used anticancer drug cisplatin. Nevertheless, the ligand precursor did not show cytotoxic activity ($\text{IC}_{50} > 200 \mu\text{M}$). Additionally, the mode of HeLa cell death induced by synthesized complex was apoptosis, seen as condensation and fragmentation of nuclei, which is consistent with the results of flow cytometry and increase of number of cells in the sub-G1 phase of the cell cycle after 24 h treatment scheme. The

effects of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$ towards cancer cells indicate the necessity for further studies with *in vitro* and/or presumably *in vivo* tests.

Data Availability

The data used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia, (grant nos. 172035 and 175011) and National Scholarship for Postdoctoral Studies of the Republic of Serbia (N. Đ. Pantelić).

Supplementary Materials

Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectrum of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$. Figure S2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$. Figure S3. coupling of protons with tin observed in ^1H NMR spectrum of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$. Figure S4. coupling of carbon atoms with tin observed in ^{13}C NMR spectrum of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$. Figure S5. IR spectrum of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$. Figure S6. HR ESI mass spectrum of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$; $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ (634.10257). Figure S7. HR ESI mass spectrum of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{CEMPD})]$; $[\text{M}+\text{K}]^+$ (650.07690). (*Supplementary Materials*)

References

- [1] P. J. Sadler and Z. Guo, "Metal complexes in medicine: design and mechanism of action," *Pure and Applied Chemistry*, vol. 70, no. 4, pp. 863–871, 1998.
- [2] J. L. Sessler, S. R. Doctrow, J. McMurry et al., *Medicinal Inorganic Chemistry, American Chemical Society Symposium Series 903*, S. J. Lippard, Ed., American Chemical Society, Washington, DC, USA, 2005.
- [3] G. N. Kaluđerović, D. J. Miljković, M. Momčilović et al., "Novel platinum(IV) complexes induce rapid tumor cell death *in vitro*," *International Journal of Cancer*, vol. 116, no. 3, pp. 479–486, 2005.
- [4] S. Mijatovic, D. Maksimovic-Ivanic, J. Radovic et al., "Aloe emodin decreases the ERK-dependent anticancer activity of cisplatin," *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*, vol. 62, no. 11, pp. 1275–1282, 2005.
- [5] M. Mubeen and S. G. Kini, "A Review on: the design and development of egfr tyrosine kinase inhibitors in cancer therapy," *International Journal of Therapeutic Applications*, vol. 5, pp. 29–37, 2012.
- [6] B. Rosenberg, "Noble metal complexes in cancer chemotherapy," *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*, vol. 91, pp. 129–150, 1978.
- [7] L. Kelland, "The resurgence of platinum-based cancer chemotherapy," *Nature Reviews Cancer*, vol. 7, no. 8, pp. 573–584, 2007.
- [8] C. A. Rabik and M. Eileen Dolan, "Molecular mechanisms of resistance and toxicity associated with platinating agents," *Cancer Treatment Reviews*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 9–23, 2007.
- [9] Y. Dolan and S. J. Lippard, "Direct cellular responses to platinum-induced DNA damage," *Chemical Reviews*, vol. 107, no. 5, pp. 1387–1407, 2007.
- [10] S. Gómez-Ruiz, D. Maksimović-Ivanic, S. Mijatović et al., "On the discovery, biological effects, and use of cisplatin and metallocenes in anticancer chemotherapy," *Bioinorganic Chemistry and Applications*, vol. 2012, Article ID 140284, 14 pages, 2012.
- [11] G. N. Kaluđerović and R. Paschke, "Anticancer metal-therapeutics in preclinical development," *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 18, no. 31, pp. 4738–4752, 2011.
- [12] I. Lakomska, M. Fandzloch, T. Muziol et al., "Synthesis, characterization and antitumor properties of two highly cytotoxic ruthenium(III) complexes with bulky triazolopyrimidine ligands," *Dalton Transactions*, vol. 42, pp. 6219–6226, 2013.
- [13] A. I. Matesans, I. Leita, and P. Souza, "Palladium(II) and platinum(II) bis(thiosemicarbazone) complexes of the 2,6-diacetylpyridine series with high cytotoxic activity in cisplatin resistant A2780cisR tumor cells and reduced toxicity," *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, vol. 125, pp. 26–31, 2013.
- [14] P. Smolenski, S. W. Jaros, C. Pettinari et al., "New water-soluble polypyridine silver(I) derivatives of 1,3,5-triaza-7-phosphaadamantane (PTA) with significant antimicrobial and antiproliferative activities," *Dalton Transactions*, vol. 42, pp. 6572–6581, 2013.
- [15] S. Nikolić, D. M. Opsenica, V. Filipović et al., "Strong *in vitro* cytotoxic potential of new ruthenium–cymene complexes," *Organometallics*, vol. 34, no. 14, pp. 3464–3473, 2015.
- [16] W. Liu and R. Gust, "Metal N-heterocyclic carbene complexes as potential antitumor metallodrugs," *Chemical Society Reviews*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 755–773, 2013.
- [17] M. Gielen, *Tin-Based Anti-Tumor Drugs*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Germany, 1990.
- [18] M. Gielen, "Tin-based antitumor drugs," *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, vol. 151, pp. 41–51, 1996.
- [19] P. Yang and M. Guo, "Interactions of organometallic anticancer agents with nucleotides and DNA," *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, vol. 185, pp. 189–211, 1999.
- [20] M. Gielen, M. Biesemans, and D. De Vos, "Synthesis, characterization and *in vitro* antitumor activity of di- and triorganotin derivatives of phospha- and biologically relevant carboxylic acids," *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, vol. 79, pp. 139–145, 2000.
- [21] M. Gielen, "Organotin compounds and their therapeutic potential," *Applied Organometallic Chemistry*, vol. 16, pp. 481–494, 2002.
- [22] S. K. Hadjikakou and N. Hadjiliadis, "Antiproliferative and anti-tumor activity of organotin compounds," *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, vol. 253, pp. 235–249, 2009.
- [23] A. K. Saxena and F. Huber, "Organotin compounds and cancer chemotherapy," *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, vol. 95, pp. 109–123, 1989.
- [24] J. Susperregui, M. Bayle, G. Lain et al., "Synthesis and evaluation of the *in vivo* trypanocidal activity of water soluble organotin compounds," *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 34, pp. 617–623, 1999.
- [25] L. Pellerito and L. Nagy, "Organotin(IV) $^{n+}$ complexes formed with biologically active ligands: equilibrium and structural studies, and some biological aspects," *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, vol. 224, pp. 111–150, 2002.
- [26] T. S. Basu Baul, W. Rynjah, E. Rivarola et al., "Synthesis and characterization of bis[dicarboxylatotetraorganodistannoxane] units involving 5-[(E)-2-(aryl)-1-diazenyl]-2-hydroxybenzoic acids: an investigation of structures by X-ray diffraction, NMR, electrospray ionisation MS and assessment of *in vitro* cytotoxicity," *Journal of Organometallic Chemistry*, vol. 691, pp. 4850–4862, 2006.
- [27] L. Tian, Y. Sun, H. Li et al., "Synthesis, characterization and biological activity of triorganotin 2-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylates," *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, vol. 99, no. 8, pp. 1646–1652, 2005.
- [28] S. Gómez-Ruiz, G. N. Kaluđerović, S. Prashar et al., "Study of the cytotoxic activity of di and triphenyltin(IV) carboxylate complexes," *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, vol. 102, no. 12, pp. 2087–2096, 2008.
- [29] D. Tzimopoulos, I. Sanidas, A.-C. Varvogli et al., "On the bioreactivity of triorganotin aminobenzoates. Investigation of trialkyl and triarylyltin(IV) esters of 3-amino and 4-amino benzoic acids," *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, vol. 104, no. 4, pp. 423–430, 2010.
- [30] M. N. Xanthopoulou, S. K. Hadjikakou, N. Hadjiliadis et al., "Synthesis, structural characterization and *in vitro* cytotoxicity of organotin(IV) derivatives of heterocyclic thioamides, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole, 5-chloro-2-mercaptobenzothiazole,

- 3-methyl-2-mercaptobenzothiazole and 2-mercaptopyridine-4-thione acid,” *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, vol. 96, pp. 425–434, 2003.
- [31] M. N. Xanthopoulou, S. K. Hadjikakou, N. Hadjiliadis et al., “Biological studies of new organotin(IV) complexes of thioamide ligands,” *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 327–335, 2008.
- [32] M. N. Xanthopoulou, S. K. Hadjikakou, N. Hadjiliadis et al., “Synthesis, structural characterization, and biological studies of six- and five-coordinate organotin(IV) complexes with the thioamides 2-mercaptobenzothiazole, 5-chloro-2-mercaptobenzothiazole, and 2-mercaptobenzoxazole,” *Inorganic Chemistry*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 1187–1195, 2007.
- [33] M. N. Xanthopoulou, S. K. Hadjikakou, N. Hadjiliadis et al., “Biological studies of organotin(IV) complexes with 2-mercaptopyrimidine,” *Russian Chemical Bulletin*, vol. 56, no. 4, pp. 767–773, 2007.
- [34] C. Ma, Q. Jiang, and R. Zhang, “Synthesis, properties and crystal structural characterization of diorganotin(IV) derivatives of 2-mercapto-6-nitrobenzothiazole,” *Applied Organometallic Chemistry*, vol. 17, no. 8, pp. 623–630, 2003.
- [35] C. Ma and J. Zhang, “Syntheses and crystal structures of diorganotin(IV) bis(2-pyridinethiolato-N-oxide) complexes,” *Applied Organometallic Chemistry*, vol. 17, no. 10, pp. 788–794, 2003.
- [36] F. Barbieri, F. Sparatore, R. Bonavia et al., “Chemosensitivity of glioblastoma cells during treatment with the organotin compound triethyltin(IV)lupinylsulfide hydrochloride,” *Journal of Neuro-Oncology*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 109–116, 2002.
- [37] E. R. T. Tiekink, “Tin dithiocarbamates: applications and structures,” *Applied Organometallic Chemistry*, vol. 22, no. 9, pp. 533–550, 2008.
- [38] M. Z. Bulatović, D. Maksimović-Ivanić, C. Bensing et al., “Organotin(IV)-loaded mesoporous silica as a biocompatible strategy in cancer treatment,” *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, vol. 53, no. 23, pp. 5982–5987, 2014.
- [39] G. Atassi, *Reviews on Silicon, Germanium, Tin and Lead Compounds*, vol. 8, 1985.
- [40] L. Tian, X. Liu, X. Zheng et al., “Synthesis, characterization, and *in vitro* cytotoxicity of organotin derivatives of 4-biphenylcarboxylic acid,” *Synthesis and Reactivity in Inorganic, Metal-Organic, and Nano-Metal Chemistry*, vol. 40, pp. 779–784, 2010.
- [41] T. S. Basu Baul, D. Dutta, A. Duthie et al., “Triphenyltin(IV) benzoates with diazenyl/imino scaffold exhibiting remarkable apoptosis mediated by reactive oxygen species,” *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, vol. 173, pp. 79–92, 2017.
- [42] T. S. Basu Baul, I. Longkumer, A. Duthie et al., “Triphenylstannyl((arylimino)methyl)benzoates with selective potency that induce G1 and G2/M cell cycle arrest and trigger apoptosis via ROS in human cervical cancer cells,” *Dalton Transactions*, vol. 47, no. 6, pp. 1993–2008, 2018.
- [43] Y.-F. Win, C.-S. Choong, J.-C. Dang et al., “Synthesis, crystal structures and spectroscopic properties of two new organotin(IV) complexes and their antiproliferative effect against cancerous and non-cancerous cells,” *Comptes Rendus Chimie*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 137–148, 2015.
- [44] K. T. Mahmudov, M. F. C. Guedes da Silva, M. N. Kopylovich et al., “Di- and tri-organotin(IV) complexes of arylhydrazones of methylene active compounds and their antiproliferative activity,” *Journal of Organometallic Chemistry*, vol. 760, pp. 67–73, 2014.
- [45] V. Dokorou, A. Primikiri, D. Kovala-Demertzi et al., “The triphenyltin(VI) complexes of NSAIDs and derivatives. Synthesis, crystal structure and antiproliferative activity. Potent anticancer agents,” *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, vol. 105, no. 2, pp. 195–201, 2011.
- [46] Y.-F. Win, S.-G. Teoh, S.-T. Ha et al., “Preliminary *in vitro* cytotoxic assay on HepG2 and antibacterial screening activity: synthesis and characterization of organotin(IV) complexes derivatives of 2-methyl-3-nitrobenzoic acid,” *Asian Journal of Chemistry*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 3376–3380, 2013.
- [47] R. L. Hudkins, D. L. DeHaven-Hudkins, and P. Doukas, “Design of dual acting anticonvulsant-antimuscarinic succinimide and hydantoin derivatives,” *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, vol. 7, no. 8, pp. 979–984, 1997.
- [48] J. Obniska, S. Rzepka, and K. Kamiński, “Synthesis and anticonvulsant activity of new N-Mannich bases derived from 3-(2-fluorophenyl)- and 3-(2-bromophenyl)-pyrrolidine-2,5-diones. Part II,” *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 20, no. 15, pp. 4872–4880, 2012.
- [49] E. Pekala, P. Liana, P. Kubowicz et al., “Evaluation of mutagenic and antimutagenic properties of new derivatives of pyrrolidine-2,5-dione with anti-epileptic activity, by use of the *Vibrio harveyi* mutagenicity test,” *Mutation Research*, vol. 758, no. 1, pp. 18–22, 2013.
- [50] I. Muszalska, “Studies of the degradation mechanism of pyrrolo[3,4-c] pyridine-1,3(2H)-dione derivatives with analgesic activity: isolation and identification of products and summary,” *Acta Poloniae Pharmaceutica*, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 233–238, 2010.
- [51] N. Matuszak, G. G. Muccioli, J. Labar et al., “Synthesis and *in vitro* evaluation of N-Substituted maleimide derivatives as selective monoglyceride lipase inhibitors,” *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 52, no. 23, pp. 7410–7420, 2009.
- [52] C. Syng-Ai, T. S. Basu Baul, and A. Chatterjee, “Inhibition of cell proliferation and antitumor activity of a novel organotin compound,” *Journal of Environmental Pathology, Toxicology and Oncology*, vol. 20, p. 333, 2001.
- [53] F. Barbieri, M. Viale, F. Sparatore et al., “Antitumor activity of a new orally active organotin compound: a preliminary study in murine tumor models,” *Anticancer Drugs*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 599–304, 2002.
- [54] H. Seibert, S. Moerchel, and M. Guelden, “Cytotoxic potency of trialkyltins to C6 glioma cells *in vitro*: impact of exposure conditions,” *Cell Biology and Toxicology*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 273–283, 2004.
- [55] H. Höti, J. Ma, S. Tabassum et al., “Triphenyl tin benzimidazolethiol, a novel antitumor agent, induces mitochondrial-mediated apoptosis in human cervical cancer cells via suppression of HPV-18 encoded E6,” *The Journal of Biochemistry*, vol. 134, no. 4, pp. 521–528, 2003.
- [56] J. Petković Cvetković, B. Đ. Božić, N. R. Banjac et al., “Synthesis, antimicrobial activity and quantum chemical investigation of novel succinimide derivatives,” *Journal of Molecular Structure*, vol. 1181, pp. 148–156, 2019.
- [57] N. Pantelić, B. B. Zmejkovski, B. Kolundžija et al., “*In vitro* antitumor activity, metal uptake and reactivity with ascorbic acid and BSA of some gold(III) complexes with *N,N'*-ethylenediamine bidentate ester ligands,” *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, vol. 172, pp. 55–66, 2017.
- [58] T. Mosmann, “Rapid colorimetric assay for cellular growth and survival: application to proliferation and cytotoxicity assays,” *Journal of Immunological Methods*, vol. 65, pp. 55–63, 1983.
- [59] M. Ohno and T. Abe, “Rapid colorimetric assay for the quantification of leukemia inhibitory factor (LIF) and interleukin-6 (IL-6),” *Journal of Immunological Methods*, vol. 145, pp. 199–203, 1991.

- [60] N. K. Banda, W. C. Satterfield, A. Dunlap A et al., "Lack of gp120-induced anergy and apoptosis in chimpanzees is correlated with resistance to AIDS," *Apoptosis*, vol. 1, pp. 49–62, 1996.
- [61] R. H. Clothier, "The FRAME cytotoxicity test (Kenacid Blue)," in *Methods in Molecular Biology, In Vitro Toxicity Testing Protocols*, S. O'Hare and C. K. Atterwill, Eds., vol. 43, pp. 109–118, Humana Press, Totowa, NJ, USA, 1995.
- [62] G. B. Deacon and R. J. Phillips, "Relationships between the carbon-oxygen stretching frequencies of carboxylato complexes and the type of carboxylate coordination," *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 227–250, 1980.
- [63] G. N. Kaluđerović, H. Kommera, E. Hey-Hawkins et al., "Synthesis and biological applications of ionic triphenyltin(IV) chloride carboxylate complexes with exceptionally high cytotoxicity," *Metallomics*, vol. 2, pp. 419–428, 2010.

Hindawi

Submit your manuscripts at
www.hindawi.com

